

Research

Evaluating the outcome of treatment using bone cement or bone graft in Giant Cell Tumor of Bone

Sakurul Islam¹, Jiazhen Li, MD^{1*}, Yan Zhang, MD¹, Xin-Chang Lu, MD¹, Yi Zhang, MD¹, Sripur Manandhar¹, Raiana Jannat Ahsan²

¹Department of Orthopedics, 1st Affiliated Hospital of Zhengzhou University, China

²Department of Endocrinology and Metabolism, 1st Affiliated Hospital of Zhengzhou University, China

***Corresponding author.**

Accepted: 14 March , 2020; **Online:** 31 March , 2020

DOI : <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3738757>

Abstract: *Introduction: Giant cell tumors exhibit a benign histological picture which has a high potential to show local aggressiveness and has the potency of incidental transformation into sarcoma. Intensive intralesional curettage followed by bone graft or bone cement filling is considered to be the standard method of treatment. We evaluated the outcome of intralesional curettage using bone graft or bone cement by observing complication free survival, recurrence, postoperative complications like stiffness, osteoarthritis, fracture during the follow up visits of the patients. Method: In the First affiliated hospital of Zhengzhou University total 105 patients having giant cell tumour of long bone were treated from January 2013 to December 2017. Among them we selected 78 patients who did not have a pathological fracture at the time of diagnosis, no metastasis and came for a post operative scheduled follow up. The patients were divided into 2 groups: Group A who had curettage with bone cement filling and Group B who had curettage with bone graft. Result: 39 patients were treated with intralesional curettage followed by bone cement filling and 39 patients were treated with intralesional curettage followed by bone graft. Bone cement has been considered to have better complication free survival than bone graft (P=0.001). 15 patients treated with bone cement filling developed their complications like local recurrence, fracture, stiffness of joint, osteoarthritis at a mean time of 23.4 months which is significantly higher (with a P=0.02) than 25 patients treated with bone graft who developed complication at a mean time of 12.5 months. The mean time of developing of local recurrence in patients who underwent bone curettage with bone cement filling is 25.2 months whereas in patients with bone graft the mean time for local recurrence is 11.4 months is significantly different (P=0.013). Internal fixation along with filling material gives a better prognosis than using the filling material alone (P=0.029). Conclusion: We evaluated that intralesional curettage following bone cement filling has lower recurrence rate and less complications compared to bone graft substitute. The possibility of development of complication*

becomes less obvious if internal fixator is used along with bone cement. This can be used for prompt and longer duration of complication free survival.

Keywords: *Giant Cell Tumor, Bone Cement, Bone Graft, Recurrence, Internal Fixation.*

Introduction

Giant cell tumors exhibit a benign histological picture which has a high potential to show local aggressiveness and has the potency of incidental transformation into sarcoma (1). It possesses explicit features involving usually the end of long bone with a substantial derangement of bone architecture that can affect adjacent peri-articular locations, and associated with a strong tendency toward local recurrence and rare capacity to metastasize to the lungs (2). The most acknowledged treatment for GCT of long bone is intensive intralesional curettage followed by bone graft or bone cement filling using polymethyl methacrylate. Formerly the treatment comprised of simple excision but the complication of recurrence was high. Henceforth, the conventional treatment focused towards local control of tumour along with preserving joint function by which has been accomplished by intralesional curettage with bone graft by iliac cortico-cancellous bone. Despite circumstantial excision, this method also reported recurrence concerning microscopic disease left in the bone and reconstruction problems (3). Giant cell tumour presents skeletal complications characterized by pain, limitation of joint movement, nerve compression, pathological fracture and lytic bone lesions (4). An epidemiological study on GCT in Chinese population reported that GCT is a rare tumour with an incidence ranging between 1.49 to 2.7 cases per million persons per year which is almost 14-20% of benign bone tumors (4,5). In Chinese population GCT occurs in young adults between 20 to 40 years of age. The most common sites for GCT is proximal tibia and distal femur which indicates that fifty percent of the GCT occurs around knee joint (6).

Bone graft or bone cement after curettage as filling material is used in giant cell tumors (7). In invasive bone tumors bone cement is used for reconstruction and cavity filling. Cementing generates heat during polymerization which destroys residual tumor cells and stabilizes the operated limb. Cementing has been reported to cause demolition of articular cartilage by thermal effect. Both grafting and cementing may cause filling defect leading to degenerative changes resulting osteoarthritis and stiffness in contiguous joint (8, 9). Bone graft is conventionally used for defect filling. Recurrence, collapse, fracture of the graft, subluxation, arthritis, damage to the articular cartilage, post surgical pneumonia has been reported in different studies. The notable

complication for using bone cement includes loosening of prosthesis, wound infection, trochanteric separation, trochanteric bursitis, bone cement implantation syndrome. Bone cement near the articular cartilage makes the patient more vulnerable to articular damage and degenerative osteoarthritis. In 24 months following surgery usually degenerative changes were observed in cases treated with bone cement but in subsequent follow up significant degenerative changes were reported. (9)

Definitive disputations arise for reaching the ultimate treatment approach for Giant cell tumour. Intralesional curettage and excision is the optimal and standard method of treatment though local recurrence is a common complication. Bone graft and bone cement both are reputable treatment option for giant cell tumor. We evaluated the outcome of intralesional curettage using bone graft or bone cement by observing complication free survival, post operative complications, recurrence during the follow up visits of the patients.

Methods:

In the First affiliated hospital of Zhengzhou University total 105 patients having giant cell tumour of long bone were treated from January 2013 to December 2017. Among them we selected 78 patients who did not have a pathological fracture at the time of diagnosis, had preoperative CT scan or MRI, no metastasis and came for a post operative scheduled follow up. The patients were divided into 2 groups: Group A who had curettage with bone cement filling and Group B who had curettage with bone graft; both the groups were treated by same group of surgeons. This study was approved by the ethics committee of 1st affiliated hospital of Zhengzhou University to get access to the patients' data for research.

Diagnostic tools:

The initial diagnosis was made using anteroposterior and lateral view of X-ray film. For further detailed evaluation CT scan or MRI was performed. All the diagnosis were confirmed by the biopsy of the excised tumor. Initial diagnosis of 49 patients by MRI, 8 patients by CT scan correspond to the biopsy results, 21 patients whose diagnosis remained questionable after either MRI or CT scan were confirmed after excisional biopsy. For MRI 1.5T and 3.0 T MR Scanner (MAGNETOM Verio, Siemens AG, Germany), the sequence of MRI was T1WI (TR 420–600 ms and TE 12–20 ms) and T2WI (TR 2500–4500 ms and TE 80–120 ms), slice thickness

was 4mm with 1 mm interval. The CT scan was done by 64-slice CT scanner (LightSpeed VCT, GE Healthcare, USA), with slice thickness of 5 mm. Expert pathologists confirmed diagnosis using the biopsy material.

Tumor volume measurement:

The anteroposterior, longitudinal and mediolateral maximum diameter were measure from preoperative CT scan and MRI. The formula used for tumor volume measurement is: $\pi/6(\text{Anteroposterior diameter} \times \text{Mediolateral diameter} \times \text{Longitudinal diameter})$.(10)

Operative method:

The surgical procedure includes intralesional curettage where tumor is exposed by opening a wide bone window; using a scraper the tumor is removed. Later on high speed burring is done to remove the residual of tumor, make the cavity smooth to eliminate the possibilities to recurrence. This is followed by using chemical adjuvant like phenol, to assure removal of residual. The cavity is filled with bone cement or bone graft. If internal fixation is used appropriate length steel plate and screw are selected and then screwed in accurate entry angle and 1 screw remains to hold the plate in correct positions and others are removed. After applying the filling component all screws are tightened.

Postoperative follow-up:

The scheduled follow up time is 1 month, 3 months, 6 months, 9 months and 12 months. A postoperative X-ray is done in the in each follow up. After one year patients are suggested to come for follow up every 6 months. Any complications which cannot be detected by X-ray were confirmed by MRI. Development of the complication was considered as the end follow up time for this study.

Statistical analysis:

The patients were divided into 2 groups as per method used for operation and also according to minimum 2 years of complication free survival. A chi square test was used to analyze statistical association. Mann-Whitney U test was used to compare the mean of developing complication in

these 2 groups of patients. SPSS version 23 was used for statistical analysis. *P* value less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results:

Among the 78 patients 50 were male and 28 were female. The age range was 9 years to 68 years with a mean age of 33.2 years. Mean tumor volume was 119.3 ml. Mean follow up time was 30.4 months ranging between 2 weeks to 72 months. Tumor sites include proximal femur in 5 cases, distal femur in 29 cases , proximal tibia 19 cases, distal tibia in 4 cases, proximal fibula in 1 case, proximal humerus in 7 cases, distal humerus in 2 cases, distal radius in 11 cases. 38 patients developed no complication during scheduled follow-up time up to 5 years and 40 patients had postoperative complications. The time of occurrence of complication ranges between 2 weeks to 55 months with a mean time of 16.6 months.

Table 1 shows clinical characteristics of patients divided into Group A had 39 patients who underwent curettage with bone cement and Group B had 39 patients who received bone graft. 3 cases of proximal femur, 20 cases of distal femur, 9 cases of proximal tibia,1 case of distal tibia,4 cases of proximal humerus, 1 case of distal humerus and 1 distal radius were in group A and 2 cases of proximal femur, 9 cases of distal femur, 10 cases of proximal tibia, 3 cases of distal tibia, 1 case of proximal fibula, 3 cases of proximal humerus, 1 case of distal humerus, and 10 cases of distal radius were in group B. Group A has 23 male and 16 female patients, group B has 27 male and 12 female patients. Of the 8 patients between 9-19 years age 6 received bone graft and 2 received bone cement; 26 patients of 20-40 years of age were treated with bone cement and 18 patients were treated with bone graft; among 26 patients more than 40 years of age 11 patients were in group A and 15 patients were in group B. Volume of tumor was a significant factor for group A and group B ($P=0.002$) 33 cases of more than 50 ml received bone cement filling and 20 patients received bone graft,6 cases less than 50 ml received bone cement and 19 patients received bone graft. 24 patients of group A and 14 patients of group B did not have complication in schedule follow up time in 5 years ; 15 patients from group A and 25 patients from group B developed complication which was statistically significant $P=0.02$.

40 patients developed post operative complication , among them 15 patients underwent curettage with bone cement filling and 25 patients with bone graft. 15 patients treated with bone cement

filling developed their complication at a mean time of 23.4 months which is significantly higher (with a $P=0.02$) than 25 patients treated with bone graft who developed complication at a mean time of 12.5 months. The mean time of developing of local recurrence in patients who underwent bone curettage with bone cement filling is 25.2 months whereas in patients with bone graft the mean time for local recurrence is 11.4 months is significantly different ($P=0.013$).

Considering 2 years survival rate, gender, age, location of tumor, volume of tumor were not statistically significant. Using bone cement filling had a better rate for 2 years complication free survival 79.5% than bone graft 43.6% and it is statistically significant ($P=0.001$). Female (64.3%) had a better 2 years complication free survival than male (60%). Patients between 20 to 40 years of age had a better prognosis rate (63.6%) than patients less than 20 years (50%) and more than 40 years of age (61.5%). Tumor more than 50ml volume (60.4%) has a worse rate of complication free survival than those with less than 50 ml (64%). Proximal femur (80%), proximal tibia (57.9%) and proximal humerus (28.6%) showed a better prognosis than distal femur (75.9%), distal tibia (25%) and distal humerus (0%) respectively. 2 years complication free survival was better in patients who had intralesional curettage with bone cement filling and internal fixation using plate and screw. Using the internal fixation along with filling material gives a better prognosis than using the filling material alone ($P=0.029$).

The post operative complications that arouse in group A patients were local recurrence in 8 cases, fracture in 5 cases, knee effusion in 1 case, and osteoporosis in 1 case and in group B 21 cases had local recurrence, 1 case fracture, 1 case osteoarthritis, 1 case had reduced bone density, 1 had joint stiffness. The recurrence rate were overall 37.2% ; in group A the rate was 10.3% and in group B the rate was 26.9% which significantly different.(Table: 3)

Presence of complication is significantly lower in patients who underwent bone curettage with bone cement filling than bone graft. Kaplan Meier survival curve showed a better survival in patients who had bone cement filling than patient who had bone graft. The local recurrence rate is also higher in patients who had bone graft. The Kaplan Meier log rank curve shows a better survival rate in patients who had bone cement filling.

Table 1: Comparison of clinical characteristics of patients of who underwent intralesional curettage with bone cement (group A) and bone graft (group B)

	Group A	Group B	
No. of Patients	39	39	Total= 78
Variables			
Gender			<i>P</i> =0.345
Male	23	27	50
Female	16	12	28
Age			<i>P</i> =0.131
<20 years	2	6	8
20-40 years	26	18	44
>40 years	11	15	26
Location of Tumour			<i>P</i> = 0.052
Proximal Femur	3	2	5
Distal Femur	20	9	29
Proximal Tibia	9	10	19
Distal Tibia	1	3	4
Proximal Fibula	0	1	1
Proximal Humerus	4	3	7
Distal Humerus	1	1	2
Distal Radius	1	10	11
Volume of tumour			<i>P</i> = 0.002
≤50 ml	6	19	25
>50 ml	33	20	53
Presence of complication			<i>P</i> = 0.23
No	24	14	
Yes	15	25	
Mean time of occurrence of 1st complication (months)	23.4	12.5	<i>P</i> =0.02
Mean time of developing local recurrence (months)	25.2	11.4	<i>P</i> =0.01

Table 2 : Factors determining 2 years complication free survival in 78 patients.

Factors	No.of patients	Complication free survival patients	Complication free survival rate	<i>P</i>
Gender				0.709
Male	50	30	60.00%	
Female	28	18	64.30%	
Age				0.76
0-19 years	8	4	50%	
20-40 years	44	28	63.60%	
>40 years	26	16	61.50%	
Volume of tumour				0.48
≤50 ml	25	16	64%	
>50 ml	53	32	60.40%	
Location of Tumour				0.08
Proximal Femur	5	4	80%	
Distal Femur	29	22	75.90%	
Proximal Tibia	19	11	57.90%	
Distal Tibia	4	1	25%	
Proximal Fibula	1	1	100%	
Proximal Humerus	7	2	28.60%	
Distal Humerus	2	0	0%	
Distal Radius	11	7	63.60%	
Filling material				0.001
Bone cement	39	31	79.50%	
Bone graft	39	17	43.60%	
Use of internal fixator and prosthesis				0.029
Bone cement	22	17	77.30%	
Bone cement and plate and screw	14	12	85.70%	
Bone cement and prosthesis	3	2	66.70%	
Bone graft	33	14	42.40%	
Bone graft and plate and screw	5	3	60%	
Bone graft and prosthesis	1	0	0%	

Table 3: Types of complications occurring in patients treated with bone cement and bone graft

	Bone cement	Bone graft	
No. of patients	15	25	
	19.2%	32.1%	<i>P</i> =0.020
Recurrence	8	21	
Fracture	5	1	
Knee Effusion	1	0	
Osteoarthritis	1	1	
Reduced Bone density	0	1	
Stiffness	0	1	
Local recurrence rate :			<i>P</i> =0.002
	Bone cement	Bone graft	
No. of patients	8	21	29
Rate	10.3%	26.9%	37.2%

Figure 1 : Kaplan-Meier log rank survival curve analyzing cumulative survival in patients received bone cement and bone graft (*P*=0.005)

Figure 2: Post-operative X-ray of Giant cell tumor of right proximal tibia treated with bone cement and internal fixation (plate and screw)

Figure 3: Post operative X-ray of Giant cell tumor of right distal femur treated with bone cement and internal fixator (plate and screw)

Discussion:

Giant cell tumors are common primary bone tumour which are typically benign but aggressive and can be potentially malignant. It usually involves the end of long bone with a substantial derangement bone architecture that can affect adjacent peri-articular locations, and associated with a strong tendency toward local recurrence. Stromal cells and multinucleated giant cells are principal elements of the tumor (11). Bone demolition leads to mechanical insufficiency resulting in pathological fracture which signifies invasive stage of disease. GCT presents with a mass when cortical degradation and tumor extension occur beyond the bone.(12)

The mean age of occurring GCT was 33.2 years in our study which is congruent with epidemiological study of GCT in Chinese population which implies that GCT is common in 20-40 years of patients. It also explained that the common site of GCT in Chinese population is the distal femur and proximal tibia and eventually affecting the knee joint. Among the 78 cases 29 were in proximal tibia and 19 were distal femur.

Intralesional curettage and en. bloc resection are the main surgical treatment options for GCTs (13). The local recurrence rate is higher in intralesional curettage and relatively low in en bloc resection but the long-term effect of en bloc resection is hazardous as it destroys joint function and prosthesis or reconstruction with graft is required for further management, hence, the intralesional curettage is the preferred treatment option for GCT. (14,15). After extraction of the tumour the high speed burrs are used for deepening the cavity and using adjuvant therapies like phenol and liquid nitrogen declines the recurrence risk (16,17). The subsequent step after removal of the tumor is to fill the cavity either with bone graft or with bone cement. The gold standard is the autologous bone graft because it fulfills the mechanical and biological criteria to of filling component and escapes the rejection and immunogenicity questions. The preferred method of grafting is allogenic bone graft. Considering the high cost and transmission of disease even after treating and sterilizing the graft and the bone substitutes like bone cement PMMA are in high demand. (18) Bone graft is preferred for young patients; in our study we had 8 cases of GCT of long bone in less than 20 years of age where 6 cases underwent intralesional curettage with bone graft.

Literatures have suggested intralesional curettage to be the better treatment option for giant cell tumour of bone. Errani C. et al (19) suggested that though curettage has a higher recurrence rate, use of adjuvants like phenol, cement giver better functional results and prognosis. Research

conducted by Frassica (20) et al. showed that mechanical strength was reestablished to 98% with bone cement filling. Kivioja (21) et. al. concluded bone cement as a better prognostic factor for giant cell tumor. Niu X (22) et al. summarized after retrospectively reviewing images from 10 years record that bone graft could not help local recurrence of GCT of extremities and the local recurrence rate was 11.1%. On the contrary Turcotte (23) et al. did not find any significant association between recurrence rate and adjuvant therapy or filling component.

As distal tibia and proximal femur are the most common site for GCTs of limb, the knee is eventually affected. After bone grafting it becomes difficult to distinguish between bone absorption and recurrence. Bone healing intervenes with the regeneration of joint function for weight bearing. Bone cement promptly heals bone lesions, restores bone integrity and enables rapid postoperative weight bearing. Proximal femur, distal femur and distal radius showed a better prognosis in our study but it was not a significant factor for determining the complication free survival. Studies showed that proximal femur and distal radius has a higher recurrence rate (19).

In our study filling material showed a significant association with minimum 2 years complication free survival. Bone cement showed better prognosis than bone graft, and the recurrence rate was lower in patients who received bone cement as filling material. After curettage and scraping the edge of the margin the cavity is filled with bone cement. The thermal effect generated after bone cement solidification which is around 80-90°C inactivates the residual tumour cavity and this mechanism reduces the recurrence rate. In our study 38.5% patients developed complication within 2 years and among them 24.4% were treated with bone graft developed local recurrence. Although recurrence rate is lower in bone cement, the rate of post operative fracture is higher than bone graft. Hypothetically, cartilage degeneration and fracture are due to thermal effect of bone cement. Fraquet et. al (24) stated that internal fixation would prevent the additional bone resorption and pathological fractures which is persuaded by pressure causing the loosening of bone cement. Internal fixation with steel plate or Steinmann pin is the latest popular methods. Toy (25) et al reported a better significant mechanical strength in bone cement combined with internal fixation using cork screw than using bone cement alone or accompanied by internal fixation with plate or Steinmann pins. Our study had 19 patients who had internal fixation with plate and screw and 14 of them had bone cement and 5 of them had bone graft (Figure 2 and 3).

8 cases treated with bone cement and internal fixator and 2 cases with bone graft and internal fixator had 2 years complication free survival ($P= 0.029$). We intend to make internal fixation mandatory after cavity filling.

Discussion:

Giant cell tumors are common primary bone tumour which are typically benign but aggressive and can be potentially malignant. It usually involves the end of long bone with a substantial derangement bone architecture that can affect adjacent peri-articular locations, and associated with a strong tendency toward local recurrence. Stromal cells and multinucleated giant cells are principal elements of the tumor (11). Bone demolition leads to mechanical insufficiency resulting in pathological fracture which signifies invasive stage of disease. GCT presents with a mass when cortical degradation and tumor extension occur beyond the bone.(12)

The mean age of occurring GCT was 33.2 years in our study which is congruent with epidemiological study of GCT in Chinese population which implies that GCT is common in 20-40 years of patients. It also explained that the common site of GCT in Chinese population is the distal femur and proximal tibia and eventually affecting the knee joint. Among the 78 cases 29 were in proximal tibia and 19 were distal femur.

Intralesional curettage and en. bloc resection are the main surgical treatment options for GCTs (13). The local recurrence rate is higher in intralesional curettage and relatively low in en bloc resection but the long-term effect of en bloc resection is hazardous as it destroys joint function and prosthesis or reconstruction with graft is required for further management, hence, the intralesional curettage is the preferred treatment option for GCT. (14,15). After extraction of the tumour the high speed burrs are used for deepening the cavity and using adjuvant therapies like phenol and liquid nitrogen declines the recurrence risk (16,17). The subsequent step after removal of the tumor is to fill the cavity either with bone graft or with bone cement. The gold standard is the autologous bone graft because it fulfills the mechanical and biological criteria to of filling component and escapes the rejection and immunogenicity questions. The preferred method of grafting is allogenic bone graft. Considering the high cost and transmission of disease even after treating and sterilizing the graft and the bone substitutes like bone cement PMMA are in high demand. (18) Bone graft is preferred for young patients, in our study we had 8 cases of

GCT of long bone in less than 20 years of age where 6 cases underwent intralesional curettage with bone graft.

Literatures have suggested intralesional curettage to be the better treatment option for giant cell tumour of bone. Errani C. et al (19) suggested that though curettage has a higher recurrence rate, use of adjuvants like phenol, cement give better functional results and prognosis. Research conducted by Frassica (20) et al. showed that mechanical strength was reestablished to 98% with bone cement filling. Kivioja (21) et. al. concluded bone cement as a better prognostic factor for giant cell tumor. Niu X (22) et al. summarized after retrospectively reviewing images from 10 years record that bone graft could not help local recurrence of GCT of extremities and the local recurrence rate was 11.1% . On the contrary Turcotte (23) et al. did not find any significant association between recurrence rate and adjuvant therapy or filling component.

As distal tibia and proximal femur are the most common site for GCTs of limb, the knee is eventually affected. After bone grafting it becomes difficult to distinguish between bone absorption and recurrence. Bone healing intervenes with the regeneration of joint function for weight bearing. Bone cement promptly heals bone lesions, restores bone integrity and enables rapid postoperative weight bearing. Proximal femur, distal femur and distal radius showed a better prognosis in our study but it was not a significant factor for determining the complication free survival. Studies showed that proximal femur and distal radius has a higher recurrence rate (19).

In our study filling material showed a significant association with minimum 2 years complication free survival. Bone cement showed better prognosis than bone graft, and the recurrence rate was lower in patients who received bone cement as filling material. After curettage and scraping the edge of the margin the cavity is filled with bone cement. The thermal effect generated after bone cement solidification which is around 80-90°C inactivates the residual tumour cavity and this mechanism reduces the recurrence rate. In our study 38.5% patients developed complication within 2 years and among them 24.4% were treated with bone graft developed local recurrence. Although recurrence rate is lower in bone cement, the rate of post operative fracture is higher than bone graft. Hypothetically, cartilage degeneration and fracture are due to thermal effect of bone cement. Fraquet et. al (24) stated that internal fixation would prevent the additional bone resorption and pathological fractures which is persuaded by pressure causing the loosening of

bone cement. Internal fixation with steel plate or Steinmann pins are the latest popular methods. Toy (25) et al reported a better significant mechanical strength in bone cement combined with internal fixation using cork screw than using bone cement alone or accompanied by internal fixation with plate or Steinmann pins. Our study had 19 patients who had internal fixation with plate and screw and 14 of them had bone cement and 5 of them had bone graft (Figure 2 and 3). 8 cases treated with bone cement and internal fixator and 2 cases with bone graft and internal fixator had 2 years complication free survival ($P= 0.029$). We intend to make internal fixation mandatory after cavity filling.

Conclusion:

We evaluated that intralesional curettage following bone cement filling has lower recurrence rate and lower complication compared to bone graft substitute. The possibility of development of complication becomes less obvious if internal fixator is used along with bone cement. For better consequence this can be used for prompt and longer duration of complication free survival. A prospective study with a longer duration of follow up to observe the outcome of bone cement and internal fixation needs to be performed.

References:

1. Yamamoto H, Ishihara S, Toda Y, Oda Y . Histone H3.3 mutation in giant cell tumor of bone: an update in pathology. *Med Mol Morphol.* 2020 Mar;53(1):1-6. doi: 10.1007/s00795-019-00238-1. Epub 2019 Nov 20.
2. Turcotte RE. Giant cell tumor of bone. *Orthop Clin North Am.* 2006 Jan;37(1):35-51
3. Raskin K.A., Schwab J.H., Mankin H.J., Springfield D.S., Hornicek F.J. Giant cell tumor of bone. *J. Am. Acad. Orthop. Surg.* 2013;21(2):118–126
4. Hongbo He, Hao Zeng, Wei Luo, Yupeng Liu, Can Zhang and Qing Liu : Surgical Treatment Options for Giant Cell Tumors of Bone Around the Knee Joint: Extended Curettage or Segmental Resection? *Front. Oncol.*, 24 September 2019
5. Alexander Liede, Rohini K. Hernandez, En-Tzu Tang, Chuang Li, Brian Bennett, Steven S. Wong, and Danielle Jandial Epidemiology of benign giant cell tumor of bone in the Chinese population. *J Bone Oncol.* 2018 Sep; 12: 96–100.
6. Ajay Puri , Manish Agarwal: Treatment of giant cell tumor of bone: Current concepts. *Indian J Orthop.* 2007 Apr-Jun; 41(2): 101–108.
7. Kai Zheng, Xiu-Chun Yu, Yong-Cheng Hu, Zhen Wang, Su-Jia Wu,⁴Zhao-Ming Ye. How to Fill the Cavity after Curettage of Giant Cell Tumors around the Knee? A Multicenter Analysis.

Chin Med J (Engl). 2017 Nov 5; 130(21): 2541–2546. doi: 10.4103/0366-6999.217093.
PMCID: PMC5678251

8. Radev BR, Kase JA, Askew MJ, Weiner SD. Potential for thermal damage to articular cartilage by PMMA reconstruction of a bone cavity following tumor excision: A finite element study. *J Biomech.* 2009;42:1120–6.
9. Szalay K, Antal I, Kiss J, Szendroi M. Comparison of the degenerative changes in weight-bearing joints following cementing or grafting techniques in giant cell tumour patients: Medium-term results. *Int Orthop.* 2006;30:505–9
10. Johanna Sápi, Levente Kovács, Dániel András Drexler, Pál Kocsis, Dávid Gajári, Zoltán Sápi. Tumor Volume Estimation and Quasi-Continuous Administration for Most Effective Bevacizumab Therapy : <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0142190>
11. Murphey MD, Nomikos GC, Flemming DJ, Gannon FH, Temple HT, Kransdorf MJ. Imaging of giant cell tumor and giant cell reparative granuloma of bone: radiologic-pathologic correlation. *RadioGraphics* 2001;21(5):1283–1309.
12. HK Manjunatha, AS Ramaswamy, and B Sunil Kumar. Aggressive giant cell tumor of the anterior arc of the rib *J Cytol.* 2012 Jan-Mar; 29(1): 51–53. doi: 10.4103/0970-9371.93224
PMCID: PMC3307453.
13. Campanacci M. Bone and soft tissue tumors. 1999 Springer-Verlag Wien.
14. XIUCHUN YU, MING XU, SONGFENG XU, and QING SU. Clinical outcomes of giant cell tumor of bone treated with bone cement filling and internal fixation, and oral bisphosphonates : *Oncol Lett.* 2013 Feb; 5(2): 447–451.
15. Prosser GH, Baloch KG, Tillman RM, Carter SR, Grimer RJ: Does curettage without adjuvant therapy provide low recurrence rates in giant-cell tumors of bone. *Clin Orthop Relat Res.* 2005, 435: 211-218.
16. Wang HC, Chien SH, Lin GT: Management of grade III giant cell tumors of bones. *J Surg Oncol.* 2005, 92: 46-51. 10.1002/jso.20338.
17. Chakarun CJ, Forrester DM, Gottsegen CJ, Patel DB, White EA, Matcuk GR: Giant cell tumor of bone: review, mimics, and new developments in treatment. *Radiographics.* 2013, 33: 197-211. 10.1148/rg.331125089
18. Gabriel Fernandez de Grado, Laetitia Keller, Ysia Idoux-Gillet, Quentin Wagner, Anne-Marie Musset, Nadia Benkirane-Jessel, Fabien Bornert, and Damien Offner. Bone substitutes: a review of their characteristics, clinical use, and perspectives for large bone defects management: *J Tissue Eng.* 2018 Jan-Dec; 9: 2041731418776819. PMCID: PMC5990883 PMID: 29899969
19. Errani C, Ruggieri P, Asenzio MA, Toscano A, Colangeli S, Rimondi E, Rossi G, Longhi A, Mercuri M. Giant cell tumor of the extremity: a review of 349 cases from a single institution. *Cancer Treat Rev.* 2010;36:1–7. doi: 10.1016/j.ctrv.2009.09.002.
20. Frassica FJ, Sim FH, Pritchard DJ, Chao EY. Subchondral replacement: a comparative analysis of reconstruction with methyl methacrylate or autogenous bone graft. *Chir Organi Mov.* 1990;75:189–190.

21. Kivioja AH, Blomqvist C, Hietaniemi K, Trovik C, Walloe A, Bauer HC, Jorgensen PH, Bergh P, Follerås G. Cement is recommended in intralesional surgery of giant cell tumors: a Scandinavian Sarcoma Group study of 294 patients followed for a median time of 5 years. *Acta Orthop*. 2008;79:86–93.
22. Niu X, Zhang Q, Hao L, Ding Y, Li Y, Xu H, Liu W. Giant cell tumor of the extremity: retrospective analysis of 621 Chinese patients from one institution. *J Bone Joint Surg Am*. 2012;94:461–467. doi: 10.2106/JBJS.J.01922.
23. Turcotte RE, Wunder JS, Isler MH, Bell RS, Schachar N, Masri BA, Moreau G, Davis AM. Giant cell tumor of long bone: a Canadian Sarcoma Group study. *Clin Orthop Relat Res*. 2002;397:248–258. doi: 10.1097/00003086-200204000-00029.
24. Fraquet N, Faizon G, Rosset P, Phillippeau JM, Waast D, Gouin F. Long bones giant cells tumors: treatment by curettage and cavity filling cementation. *Orthop Traumatol Surg Res*. 2009;95:402–406
25. Toy PC, France J, Randall RL, Neel MD, Shorr RI, Heck RK. Reconstruction of noncontained distal femoral defects with polymethylmethacrylate and crossed-screw augmentation: a biomechanical study. *J Bone Joint Surg Am*. 2006;88:171–178.
26. Szendroi M, Kiss J, Antal I. Surgical treatment and prognostic factors in giant-cell tumor of bone. *Acta Chir Orthop Traumatol Cech*. 2003;70:142–150.

Sakurul Islam.

Completed MBBS from University of Dhaka, Bangladesh.

Currently MS student at 1st Affiliated Hospital of Zhengzhou University.

Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

© 2020 by the authors. TWASP, NY, USA. Author/authors are fully responsible for the text, figure, data in above pages. This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)

